

mondo

THE WORLD'S DISEASE CONCEPTS, UNIFIED

Epilepsy Workshop

Nicole Vasilevsky and Sabrina Toro
October 25, 2024

Your facilitators

Nicole Vasilevsky

Associate Director of Data Science
DCC, Critical Path Institute

Sabrina Toro

Lead Biocurator
TISLab, University of North Carolina

Welcome!

Time	Agenda Item
8:00 AM PT / 11:00 AM ET	Logistics and code of conduct
8:05 AM PT / 11:05 AM ET	Introduce attendees
8:15 AM PT / 11:15 AM PT	Introduction to Mondo and the problem
8:30 AM PT / 11:30 AM ET	Epilepsy classification top level classification + questions about terms of interest
9:15 AM PT / 12:15 PM ET	Review term definitions for specific terms of interest
10:00 AM PT / 1:00 PM ET	Adjournment

WORKSHOP GOALS

1

Review how to contribute to the Mondo disease ontology using GitHub

2

Upper level classification of epilepsy disease branch/alignment with ILAE

3

Review classification and definitions of key terms of interest

4

(Part 2/Time allowing) Review classification of terms as diseases and/or phenotypes

5

Build collaborations and strengthen the community with experts in the field

Introductions

Monarch: connecting diseases, phenotypes, and genes

MONARCH INITIATIVE

Accelerating precision medicine through Open Data Science

HPO

The standard vocabulary of human phenotypic abnormalities.

Mondo

Harmonizing disease definitions globally.

Exomiser

A tool to find potential disease-causing variants in WES and WGS.

Uberon

An integrated cross-species anatomy ontology.

Knowledge Graph

Explore gene, disease, and phenotype data across species.

Phenopackets

An ISO-endorsed open standard for sharing disease and phenotype information.

<https://monarchinitiative.org/>

Why do we need a (disease) ontology?

Having this information in an ontology promotes utilization of standardized terminology for diagnostics, clinical management, research into novel variants, and more

Mondo Disease Ontology

- Over 20,000 disease terms
- 18 source terminologies

<https://mondo.monarchinitiative.org/pages/sources/>

	ID Space	Role	Website
1 + 2. OMIM + Phenotypic series	OMIM/OMIMPS	Source	omim.org
3. Orphanet	Orphanet	Source	https://www.orpha.net/
4. Genetic and Rare Diseases Information Center	GARD	Source	rarediseases.info.nih.gov
5. SNOMED	SNOMED	xref/Alignments	snomed.org
6. National Cancer Institute Thesaurus	NCIT	Source	ncit.nci.nih.gov
7. Medical Subject Headings	MESH	Source	nlm.nih.gov/mesh/
8. Unified Medical Language System	UMLS	xref/Alignments	nlm.nih.gov/research/umls/index.html
9 + 10 + 11. Int'l Classification of Diseases 9/10/11 Foundation	ICD9/10/11.foundation	xref/Alignments	cdc.gov/nchs/icd/icd9.htm cdc.gov/nchs/icd/icd10cm.htm https://icd.who.int/dev11/
12. Experimental Factor Ontology	EFO	xref/Alignments	ebi.ac.uk/efo/
13. Disease Ontology	DO	Source	obofoundry.org/ontology/doid.html
14. Mental Functioning Ontology	MF	xref/Alignments	obofoundry.org/ontology/mf.html
15. MedGen	MEDGEN	xref/Alignments	ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/medgen/
16. Ontology for General Medical Science	OGMS	xref/Alignments	github.com/OGMS/ogms
17. Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities	MEDRA	xref/Alignments	meddra.org/
18. OncoTree	ONCOTREE	xref/Alignments	oncotree.mskcc.org

Hierarchical Classification of Terms

Classification approach in Mondo

The child term **must** inherit all of the properties of the parent. Eg 'peroxisomal disease' is a type of metabolic disease: it has a distinct metabolic abnormality that has been demonstrated to be associated with a substantially increased risk of developing epilepsy. Metabolic disorders have genetic origin; however, the metabolic abnormalities are a separate disorder interposed between the genetic defect and the epilepsy.

Classification approach
in Mondo: **we do not**
classify terms based on
phenotypic features

“**Seizures**, reported in 30%, can include tonic-clonic seizures, absence seizures, and complex partial epilepsy.” PMID: 20945554

Mondo Stats

25,225 disease terms

126,890
Database cross reference

17,229
Term definitions

73,090 Exact synonyms

2,536 Narrow synonyms

30,434 Related synonyms

1,374 Broad synonyms

15,630

Rare diseases

1,071

Infectious diseases

4,713

Cancers (including neoplasms)

11,307

Mendelian diseases

Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO)

- **Standardized, machine readable vocabulary of phenotypic abnormalities**

>14,500 terms

- **Computational disease models**

>190,000 disease-phenotype annotations (associations)

- **Widely adopted in rare disease genomic diagnostic tools**

100,000 Genomes Project, SOLVE-RD, NIH-UDP, etc.

monarchinitiative.org/hpo

[Nature Genetics 50, 474–476](#)

>14,500 terms
representing biological
features

Translated into many
languages

Computational disease
models

>190,000
disease-phenotype
annotations (associations)

Widely adopted (100,000
Genomes Project,
SOLVE-RD, UDN, UDP, etc.)

Where to view Mondo

OLS > MONDO: Monarch Disease Ontology | MONDO > MONDO:0019249

mucopolysaccharidosis

http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MONDO_0019249

A group of autosomal recessive or X-linked inherited lysosomal storage disorders affecting the metabolism of mucopolysaccharides, resulting in the accumulation of mucopolysaccharides in the body. Signs and symptoms include organomegaly, mental retardation, abnormal skeletal development, heart disorders, hearing loss, and central nervous system deficiencies. [NCIT:C61259]

Tree view | Term history

- disease or disorder
 - congenital abnormality
 - developmental defect during embryogenesis
 - developmental anomaly of metabolic origin
 - mucopolysaccharidosis**
- disease by anatomical system
 - nervous system disorder
 - congenital nervous system disorder
 - mucopolysaccharidosis**
 - genetic nervous system disorder
 - rare genetic eye disease
 - rare disease with glaucoma as a major feature
 - mucopolysaccharidosis**

- mucopolysaccharidoses, unclassified types
- mucopolysaccharidosis type 1**
 - Sanfilippo syndrome type A
 - Sanfilippo syndrome type B
 - Sanfilippo syndrome type C
 - Sanfilippo syndrome type D
- mucopolysaccharidosis type 4**
- mucopolysaccharidosis type 6**
- mucopolysaccharidosis type 7**
- mucopolysaccharidosis type 9**
- mucopolysaccharidosis with skin involvement**
- mucopolysaccharidosis-like syndrome with congenital heart defects and hematopoietic disorders
- perceptual disorders
- vision disorder
- eye disease

Graph view | Reset tree | Show all siblings

Term info

database cross reference

- SCTID:11380006 (MONDO:kboom-pr-1.00/0.86/15.45)
- COHD:433446 (MONDO:equivalentTo)
- UMLS:C0026703 (Orphanet:79213)
- ICD10:E76.2 (Orphanet:79213)
- ICD10:E76.0 (Orphanet:79213)
- NCIT:C61259 (MONDO:kboom-pr-1.00/0.87/15.87)
- ICD10:E76.1 (Orphanet:79213)
- Orphanet:79213 (MONDO:equivalentTo)
- DOID:12798 (MONDO:equivalentTo)
- MESH:D009083 (Orphanet:79213)
- OMIMPS:607014 (MONDO:equivalentTo)
- GARD:0007065 (MONDO:equivalentTo)
- ICD10:E76.3 (Orphanet:79213)
- ICD9:277.5 (I2s)
- MedDRA:10028093 (Orphanet:79213)

Subsets

gard_rare, ordo_group_of_disorders

closeMatch

<http://identifiers.org/snomedct/267452003>,
<http://identifiers.org/snomedct/190942001>,
<http://identifiers.org/snomedct/190936000>

summary

term info

hierarchy

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/mondo>

OBO Foundry
obofoundry.org/ontology/mondo

Ontology Lookup Service
ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/mondo

GitHub
github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo

Protege
download OWL file from GitHub

Mondo community

GitHub

github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo
>8000 issues reported

Mondo users list

<https://groups.google.com/forum/#!forum/mondo-users>

Email

info@monarchinitiative.org

Community developed

Outreach Calls

Fridays, every 4 weeks, 9am PT/12pm ET
Zoom

Workshops

<https://mondo.monarchinitiative.org/pages/workshop/>

Emails to the
Mondo users
list often
come with
pet pictures
attached
*(please share
your pics!)*

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Frequently requested changes to Mondo

add a new term

A new term is added to Mondo, for example, pythiosis.

relabel a term

For example, rename endometriosis of uterus to adenomyosis

reclassify a term

For example, adenoma of pancreas is as subclass of adenoma.

obsolete a term

A term is obsoleted because it is considered out of scope in Mondo.

merge terms

Okamoto syndrome is merged with Au-Klein syndrome

split a term

Birt-Hogg-Dube syndrome is split into Birt-Hogg-Dube syndrome and Birt-Hogg-Dube syndrome 1

How to request new terms (Mondo IDs) & changes

1. GitHub tracker: New issue
2. Pick appropriate template
3. Fill in the information that is requested on the template below each header
4. Please include:
 - a. A definition in the proper format
 - b. Sources/cross references for synonyms
 - c. Your ORCID or the URL for your ClinGen working group
 - d. Add any additional comments at the end
5. A curator will automatically be tagged
6. Please comment on the ticket if the ticket is high priority

Recommendations for GitHub tickets/new term requests

We appreciate your contributions to extending and improving Mondo

General Recommendations:

1. New term requests should not match existing terms or synonyms
2. Write a concise definition in the definition field. More info about writing definitions is [here](#)
3. Synonyms - please provide a source/cross-reference
4. Check OMIM for children classes

Formatting:

1. Preferred term labels should be lowercase (unless it is a proper name or abbreviation)
2. Write the request below the prompts on the template so the Markdown formatting displays properly
3. Synonyms should be lowercase (with exceptions above)
4. Definition source - if from PubMed, please use the format PMID:XXXXXX (no space)
5. Include the Mondo ID and label for the parent term
6. List the children terms with Mondo ID and label in a bulleted list

LET'S GET TO

WORK. MEOW

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Epilepsy classification in Mondo: Initial work to align with the ILAE at lower levels

Upper level classification

Example revisions to classification according to ILAE

Dark border = new classification

Yellow fill – Terms are in ILAE

Grey fill = Terms are in Mondo but not mentioned in ILAE

etc...

**Let's start by
focusing on top
level of the Mondo
epilepsy
classification**

What do we currently have in Mondo?

Epilepsy

EPILEPSY TYPE

Focal epilepsy

Generalized epilepsy

Combined Generalized & Focal epilepsy

Epilepsy, unknown type

Epilepsy syndrome

EPILEPSY ETIOLOGY

Structural epilepsy

Genetic epilepsy

Infectious epilepsy

Metabolic epilepsy

Immune epilepsy

Unknown etiology epilepsy

Mondo Epilepsy Classification

epilepsy

- autoimmune epilepsy
- electroclinical syndrome
- epilepsia partialis continua
- **epilepsy syndrome**
- epilepsy, idiopathic generalized
- extratemporal epilepsy
- **focal epilepsy**
- **generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus**
- **immune epilepsy**
- infantile-onset epilepsy
- **monogenic epilepsy**
- post-traumatic epilepsy
- status epilepticus
- **structural epilepsy**
- variable age onset epilepsy

What do we currently have in Mondo?

Epilepsy

EPILEPSY TYPE

Focal epilepsy

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Epilepsy, unknown type

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EPILEPSY ETIOLOGY

Structural epilepsy

Genetic epilepsy

Infectious epilepsy

Metabolic epilepsy

Immune epilepsy

Unknown etiology epilepsy

Mondo Epilepsy Classification

epilepsy

We have a mix of epilepsy types, etiology and other classifications

- immune epilepsy
- proclinical syndrome
- autism partialis continua
- **epilepsy syndrome**
- epilepsy, idiopathic generalized
- temporal epilepsy
- **epilepsy**
- **generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures**
- **immune epilepsy**
- infantile-onset epilepsy
- **genetic epilepsy**
- post-traumatic epilepsy
- status epilepticus
- **structural epilepsy**
- variable age onset epilepsy

Does this diagram mean....

... every type has an etiology?

Focal	Generalized	Combined Generalized & Focal	Unknown
Structural Focal	Structural Generalized	Structural Combined Generalized & Focal	Structural Unknown
Genetic Focal	Genetic Generalized	Genetic Combined Generalized & Focal	Genetic Unknown
Infectious Focal	Infectious Generalized	Infectious Combined Generalized & Focal	Infectious Unknown
Metabolic Focal	Metabolic Generalized	Metabolic Combined Generalized & Focal	Metabolic Unknown
Immune Focal	Immune Generalized	Immune Combined Generalized & Focal	Immune Unknown
Unknown Focal	Unknown Generalized	Unknown Combined Generalized & Focal	

Or should we
have an upper
level hierarchy
like this?

These are phenotypes

- epilepsy
- autoimmune epilepsy
- electroclinical syndrome
- epilepsia partialis continua
- ★ ● epilepsy syndrome
- ● epilepsy, idiopathic generalized
- extratemporal epilepsy
- focal epilepsy
- generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus
- immune epilepsy
- infantile-onset epilepsy
- metabolic epilepsy
- monogenic epilepsy
- post-traumatic epilepsy
- status epilepticus
- structural epilepsy
- variable age onset epilepsy

-
- epilepsy
 - autoimmune epilepsy
 - electroclinical syndrome
 - epilepsy partialis continua
 - epilepsy syndrome
 - epilepsy, idiopathic generalized
 - extratemporal epilepsy
 - ★ ● focal epilepsy
 - ★ ● generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus
 - immune epilepsy
 - infantile-onset epilepsy
 - metabolic epilepsy
 - monogenic epilepsy
 - post-traumatic epilepsy
 - status epilepticus
 - structural epilepsy
 - variable age onset epilepsy

We have focal epilepsy. ✓ Next let's review generalized epilepsy according to ILAE.

- ▼ ● **generalized epilepsy**
Epilepsy that is characterized by generalized seizure types and may have typical interictal and/or ictal EEG findings that accompany generalized seizure types (for example generalized spike-wave).
- ▼ ● **genetic generalized epilepsy**
- **idiopathic generalized epilepsy**
- **generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus**

This seems okay to add to Mondo as is. ✓

Red text = From ILAE

▼ ● **generalized epilepsy**

▼ ● **genetic generalized epilepsy**

An instance of generalized epilepsy that is caused by an inherited genomic modification in an individual. **This does not always mean that the epilepsy is inherited or can be transmitted to offspring, as the genetic etiology may be a de novo pathogenic variant, or the genetic etiology may have complex/polygenic inheritance.**

● **idiopathic generalized epilepsy**

● **generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus**

In Mondo, we would use the naming 'hereditary generalized epilepsy'

- ▼ ● **generalized epilepsy**
 - **genetic generalised epilepsy**
 - **idiopathic generalized epilepsy**
ILAE def: The idiopathic generalized epilepsies are a subgroup of the genetic generalised epilepsies and compose four epilepsy syndromes childhood absence epilepsy, juvenile absence epilepsy, juvenile myoclonic epilepsy and epilepsy with generalized tonic-clonic seizures alone. These epilepsy syndromes have polygenic inheritance with or without environmental factors contributing to seizure susceptibility. Seizure types include one or a combination of absence seizures, myoclonic seizures and/or generalized tonic-clonic seizures.

This definition of idiopathic is inconsistent with the Mondo definition of idiopathic: A disease characteristic in which the disease has an uncertain or unknown cause. (MONDO:0700005)

● **combined generalized and focal epilepsy**
ILAE def: Patients may have both generalized and focal seizure types, with interictal and/or ictal EEG findings that accompany both seizure types. Patients with Dravet syndrome and Lennox-Gastaut syndrome may have combined focal and generalized epilepsy.

Note - this does not appear to have any subtypes.

We would not classify Dravet or LGS as a subtype since the definitions says they *may* have combined focal and generalized epilepsy.

unknown epilepsy

ILAE def: The term 'unknown' is used to denote where it is understood that the patient has epilepsy, but it is not possible to denote whether it is focal, generalized, or combined focal and generalized. This may occur due to insufficient information to classify the epilepsy, for example if the EEG is normal/uninformative.

For data annotation purposes, if it is unknown, we recommend using the parent class MONDO:0005027 epilepsy

Or

We could add a class called 'idiopathic epilepsy'

Proposal:

- Add terms
 - generalized epilepsy
 - hereditary generalized epilepsy
 - combined generalized and focal epilepsy
- Do not add
 - idiopathic generalized epilepsy
 - unknown epilepsy

Old hierarchy

New hierarchy

- epilepsy
- autoimmune epilepsy
- electroclinical syndrome
- epilepsia partialis continua
- epilepsy syndrome
- epilepsy, idiopathic generalized
- extratemporal epilepsy
- focal epilepsy
- generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus
- ★ ● immune epilepsy
- infantile-onset epilepsy
- ★ ● metabolic epilepsy
- ★ ● monogenic epilepsy
- post-traumatic epilepsy
- status epilepticus
- ★ ● structural epilepsy
- variable age onset epilepsy

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

infectious epilepsy

ILAE def: The commonest etiology for epilepsy worldwide is infectious, especially in developing countries. Infections in the central nervous system can cause both acute symptomatic (provoked) seizures (which occur closely related to the timing of the initial infection) and epilepsy. Infectious etiologies include tuberculosis, HIV, cerebral malaria, neurocysticercosis, subacute sclerosing panencephalitis, cerebral toxoplasmosis. These infections sometimes have a structural correlate, however the primary cause of the epilepsy is conceptualized as the infectious process. An infectious etiology may have specific treatment implications. There are also public health implications as prevention of such infections may reduce the burden of epilepsy, particularly in developing countries.

- bacterial meningitis (MONDO:0006670) or meningoencephalitis (MONDO:0005845)
- cerebral malaria (MONDO:0005625)
- cerebral toxoplasmosis (MONDO:0005697)
- CMV (MONDO:0005132)
- HIV (MONDO:0005109)
- neurocysticercosis (MONDO:0015484)
- tuberculosis (MONDO:0018076)
- viral encephalitis (MONDO:0006009)
- other infections

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

- ▼ ● **infectious epilepsy**
 - bacterial meningitis (MONDO:0006670) or meningoencephalitis (MONDO:0005845)
 - cerebral malaria (MONDO:0005625)
 - cerebral toxoplasmosis (MONDO:0005697)
 - CMV (MONDO:0005132)
 - HIV (MONDO:0005109)
 - neurocysticercosis (MONDO:0015484)
 - tuberculosis (MONDO:0018076)
 - viral encephalitis (MONDO:0006009)
 - other infections

These are subclasses of 'infectious disease' that may have seizures as a feature but are not types of epilepsy

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

Decision for us:

- A. Add infectious epilepsy as a new term but without any children terms
- B. Do not add 'infectious epilepsy' as a new term to Mondo

Proposed definition:

An epilepsy directly resulting from the presence and activity of a microbial, viral, or parasitic agent. Infections in the central nervous system can cause both acute symptomatic (provoked) seizures (which occur closely related to the timing of the initial infection) and epilepsy. Infectious etiologies ~~include~~ **may be caused by infection from** tuberculosis, HIV, cerebral malaria, neurocysticercosis, subacute sclerosing panencephalitis, cerebral toxoplasmosis. These infections sometimes have a structural correlate, however the primary cause of the epilepsy is conceptualized as the infectious process. An infectious etiology may have specific treatment implications. There are also public health implications as prevention of such infections may reduce the burden of epilepsy, particularly in developing countries.

▼ ● **idiopathic epilepsy**

ILAE def: 'Unknown' is meant to be viewed neutrally and to designate that the nature of the underlying cause of the epilepsy is as yet unknown; this may be because it has not been investigated, or because all current investigation has failed to identify the etiology.

- **Rasmussen syndrome (Rasmussen subacute encephalitis MONDO:0016019)**
- **febrile infection-related epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0015584)**

Proposal:

Proposed definition:

Idiopathic form of epilepsy. The underlying cause of the epilepsy may be because it has not been investigated, or because all current investigation has failed to identify the etiology.

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

- epilepsy
- autoimmune epilepsy
- electroclinical syndrome
- epilepsia partialis continua
- epilepsy syndrome
- epilepsy, idiopathic generalized
- extratemporal epilepsy
- focal epilepsy
- generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus
- immune epilepsy
- infantile-onset epilepsy
- metabolic epilepsy
- monogenic epilepsy
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- status epilepticus
- ★ ● structural epilepsy
- variable age onset epilepsy

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

Common structural brain abnormalities associated with epilepsy are presented in this section of EpilepsyDiagnosis.org:

- malformations of cortical development
- vascular malformations
- hippocampal sclerosis
- hypoxic-ischemic structural abnormalities
- traumatic brain injury
- tumors
- porencephalic cyst

These are not types of epilepsies but structural abnormalities that may cause epilepsy.

Proposal: no action needed.

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

There are many ways in which genetic factors can contribute to the development of epilepsy. Certain genetic factors may not have been inherited and may not be transmissible to offspring.

- inherited gene abnormalities
- autosomal dominant
- autosomal recessive
- Mendelian inheritance
- acquired gene abnormalities
 - de novo
 - sporadic
 - mosaicism
 - germline
 - somatic
- polygenic/complex genetic etiology

- inherited gene abnormalities
- autosomal dominant
- autosomal recessive
- Mendelian inheritance
- acquired gene abnormalities
 - de novo
 - sporadic
 - mosaicism
 - germline
 - somatic
- polygenic/complex genetic etiology

In Mondo, we have infer terms as monogenic epilepsies. We don't have specific grouping classes for subtypes of monogenic (autosomal dominant, etc.)

Proposal: Discuss if we need further groupings within this hierarchy?

Specific use case: MONDO:0001734 'tuberous sclerosis'

SubClass Of

'autosomal dominant disease'				
'disease has feature' some hamartoma				
'has characteristic' some inherited				
'hereditary neoplastic syndrome'				
'neurocutaneous syndrome'				
'hereditary neurological disease'				

- Tuberous sclerosis can be inherited or caused by de novo mutations
- There was a question if cases that are caused by de novo mutations should be represented differently in the ontology
- From the discussion, we concluded a de novo mutation is still considered monogenic and we should leave the hierarchy as it is

Etiology

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Immune

Unknown

- epilepsy
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- immune epilepsy
- infantile-onset epilepsy
- ★ ● metabolic epilepsy
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- structural epilepsy
- variable age onset epilepsy

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

metabolic epilepsy

- biotinidase and holocarboxylase synthase deficiency
- cerebral folate deficiency
- creatine disorders
- **folinic acid responsive seizures (MONDO:0019197)**
- **glucose transporter 1 deficiency syndrome (GLUT1DS) MONDO:0000188)**
- mitochondrial disorders
- peroxisomal disorders
- **pyridoxine-dependent (ALDH7A1)-DEE (MONDO:0020741)**
- **pyridox(am)ine 5'-phosphate oxidase (PNPO) deficiency (MONDO:0012407)**

Proposal: no action needed.

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

- epilepsy
- autoimmune epilepsy
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- epilepsy syndrome
- epilepsy, idiopathic generalized
- extratemporal epilepsy
- focal epilepsy
- generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus
- ★ ● immune epilepsy
- infantile-onset epilepsy
- metabolic epilepsy
- monogenic epilepsy
- post-traumatic epilepsy
- status epilepticus
- structural epilepsy
- variable age onset epilepsy

Proposal: These are not actual types of epilepsy, they are diseases that have seizures a feature. There is a proposal to obsolete 'antibody mediated epilepsy', I think we should proceed with that.

End of Part 1

mondo

THE WORLD'S DISEASE CONCEPTS, UNIFIED

Epilepsy Workshop Part 2:

November 22, 2024

Your facilitators

Nicole Vasilevsky

Associate Director of Data Science
DCC, Critical Path Institute

Sabrina Toro

Lead Biocurator
TISLab, University of North Carolina

Welcome!

Time	Agenda Item
8:00 AM PT / 11:00 AM ET	Welcome, logistics and code of conduct
8:10 AM PT / 11:05 AM ET	Introduce attendees
8:15 AM PT / 11:15 AM PT	Summary of Part 1
8:30 AM PT / 11:30 AM ET	Epilepsy classification top level classification + questions about terms of interest
9:50 AM PT / 1:00 PM ET	Adjournment

- Part 1 content
- Part 2 content/
New questions

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Build collaborations and strengthen the community with experts in the field

Part 1 Summary

Recording available here:

<https://mondo.monarchinitiative.org/pages/workshop/#Oct-2024>

Critical Path Institute

- **Nicole Vasilevsky, Critical Path Institute**
- Emily Hartley, Critical Path Institute
- Heidi Grabenstatter, Critical Path Institute

Monarch Initiative

- **Sabrina Toro, University of North Carolina/TISLab**
- Daniel Korn, University of North Carolina/TISLab
- Julie McMurry, University of North Carolina/TISLab
- Sarah Gehrke, University of North Carolina/TISLab
- Yousif Shwetar, University of North Carolina/TISLab
- Chris Mungall, Lawrence Berkeley National Lab

External stakeholders

- Chrystallena Sofocleous, Laboratory of Medical Genetics, School of Medicine, National & Kapodistrian University of Athens
- Jacqueline French, NYU Langone
- Subit Barua, West Virginia University School of Medicine
- Vanessa Vogel, Independent consultant/ Rare Epilepsy Network
- Tracy Dixon-Salazar, LGS Foundation

Introductions

ILAE high level classifications

ILAE high level classifications

Legend

- ★ New term added
- ★ Relabel and reclassification
- ★ Reclassification

ORIGINAL HIERARCHY

- epilepsy
 - autoimmune epilepsy
 - electroclinical syndrome
 - epilepsia partialis continua
 - epilepsy syndrome
 - epilepsy, idiopathic generalized
 - extratemporal epilepsy
 - focal epilepsy
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus
 - immune epilepsy
 - infantile-onset epilepsy
 - metabolic epilepsy
 - monogenic epilepsy
 - post-traumatic epilepsy
 - status epilepticus
 - structural epilepsy

NEW REVISIONS

- focal epilepsy
 - combined generalized and focal epilepsy
 - complex partial epilepsy
 - familial partial epilepsy
 - frontal lobe epilepsy
 - partial motor epilepsy
 - partial sensory epilepsy
 - simple partial epilepsy
- ★ ● generalized epilepsy
 - combined generalized and focal epilepsy
 - ★ ● juvenile myoclonic epilepsy
 - myoclonic epilepsy, juvenile, 2
 - ★ ● genetic generalized epilepsy
 - ★ ● hereditary generalized epilepsy
 - ★ ● generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus
 - febrile seizures, familial, 8
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 1
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 10
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 12
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 2
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 4
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 6
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 7
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 8
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 9
 - ★ ● idiopathic generalized epilepsy
 - ★ ● childhood absence epilepsy
 - ★ ● epilepsy with generalized tonic-clonic seizures
 - ★ ● juvenile absence epilepsy
 - ★ ● juvenile myoclonic epilepsy

Legend

- ★ New term added
- ★ Relabel and reclassification
- ★ Reclassification

- ★ ● idiopathic generalized epilepsy
- ★ ● childhood absence epilepsy
- ★ ● epilepsy with generalized tonic-clonic seizures
- ★ ● juvenile absence epilepsy
- ★ ● juvenile myoclonic epilepsy

- It turned out we actually had ‘idiopathic generalized epilepsy’ in Mondo already
 - It referred to an epilepsy with idiopathic origin (we removed this because our definition of idiopathic did not align with ILAE)
- I renamed it to ‘idiopathic generalized epilepsy’ (instead of generalized epilepsy, idiopathic) to match ILAE
- ILAE has four classes as children of ‘idiopathic generalized epilepsy’, which I reclassified

Legend

- ★ New term added
- ★ Relabel and reclassification
- ★ Reclassification

Should '**juvenile myoclonic epilepsy**' be a child of 'combined generalized and focal epilepsy'?

Current parents:

- **adolescence-adult electroclinical syndrome** (source: [DOID:4890](#))
- **adolescent /adult-onset epilepsy syndrome** (source: Ingo)
- **familial partial epilepsy** (source: [Orphanet:307](#))
- **idiopathic generalized epilepsy** (source: [ILAE](#))
- ***childhood electroclinical syndrome*** (inferred because of assertion of 'adolescence-adult electroclinical syndrome')
- ***combined generalized and focal epilepsy*** (inferred because of assertion of familial partial epilepsy)

Proposal: The current ILAE only classifies '**juvenile myoclonic epilepsy**' term as a child of idiopathic generalized epilepsy. Propose to remove all of the other superclasses (and the inferred superclasses will go away.)

Note: ILAE does not have any subtypes of 'combined generalized and focal epilepsy'.

This brings up a question about electroclinical syndrome - see next slide.

MONDO:0000411 electroclinical syndrome

This website talks about electroclinical syndromes in ILAE, but I can't see when this was published and electroclinical syndromes are not mentioned on the current ILAE website

Question:

- Do we want to obsolete 'electroclinical syndrome' grouping class?
- We could follow up with ILAE authors and ask their opinion

New ICE Terminology from ILAE

Important Changes in Intractable Childhood Epilepsy Terminology – International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE)

The ILAE has recently updated their classification of the epilepsy syndromes. The definitions they have listed on their website pertaining to "disease" and "syndrome" and "electro-clinical syndrome" are below: www.ilae-epilepsy.org

Disease versus syndrome: Although there is reason to distinguish the concepts of disease and syndrome, these terms are not consistently used in medicine. Ultimately, it was decided not to insist on the disease-syndrome distinction in referring to the epilepsies at this time, although either or both terms may be used depending on the context and custom. Instead, there are at least four groupings that may be invoked in this context and as described below:

Electroclinical syndromes: An electroclinical syndrome is a complex of clinical features, signs and symptoms that together define a distinctive, recognizable clinical disorder. These often become the focus of treatment trials as well as of genetic, neuropsychological, and neuroimaging investigations (e.g. Guerrini R et al., 2007, Ottman et al., 2008, Scheffer IE et al., 1998, Scheffer IE et al., 2008).

Use of the term "syndrome," and more precisely "electro-clinical syndrome," will be restricted to a group of clinical entities that are reliably identified by a cluster of electro-clinical and developmental characteristics. These are largely but not exclusively genetic in origin, and tend to have a strong relationship to developmental aspects of the brain. These are distinctive disorders identifiable on the basis of a typical age onset, specific EEG characteristics, seizure types, and often other features which, when taken together, permit a specific diagnosis. The diagnosis in turn often has implications for treatment, management, and prognosis. The term for these entities is "*Electro-clinical Syndromes.*" While ultimately common usage will likely shorten the term again to "syndrome" alone, this is still specifically defined to mean entities that can be considered *electro-clinical syndromes.* It would be inappropriate to refer to, for example, epilepsy with a frontal lobe focus and not otherwise specified as a "syndrome."

<https://www.ice-epilepsy.org/new-ice-terminology-from-ilae.html>

Epilepsy of unknown type

Epilepsy of unknown type

Epilepsy by Etiology Summary

- We have 4 of the subtypes by etiology noted above
- We reviewed the other two missing types

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

- We decided we did not need an ‘infectious epilepsy’ term
- We did not make a decision about the ‘epilepsy, unknown etiology’ term - we can discuss now

- We decided we did not need an ‘infectious epilepsy’ term
- We did not make a decision about the ‘epilepsy, unknown etiology’ term - we can discuss now

Proposal:

- Based on the discussion in Part 1 regarding epilepsy of unknown type, we should not include a term that is ‘epilepsy due to unknown etiology’
- *if needed*, we could create one *but* it would represent that every tests have been done, and we still don't know what the etiology is

- No action needed for the structural or metabolic epilepsy
- We will revisit the immune and genetic epilepsy branch below

Proposal:

- 'autoimmune epilepsy' should be a child of 'immune epilepsy'
 - Currently is a subclass of 'epilepsy'

Genetic epilepsy (by etiology)

From ILAE: There are many ways in which genetic factors can contribute to the development of epilepsy. Certain genetic factors may not have been inherited and may not be transmissible to offspring.

- inherited gene abnormalities
- autosomal dominant
- autosomal recessive
- Mendelian inheritance
- acquired gene abnormalities
 - de novo
 - sporadic
 - mosaicism
 - somatic
- germline
- polygenic/complex genetic etiology

Representation of Hereditary Diseases in Mondo

Currently in Mondo:

Hereditary disease (MONDO:0003847)

Definition: A disease that is caused by genetic modifications where those modifications are inherited from a parent's genome.

Comment: Usage note: this is intended only for diseases with an inherited genetic etiology. Somatic genetic mutations are excluded. Some ontologies use the term 'genetic disease' in the sense of inherited disorders only, we are here careful to distinguish.

Broad synonym: genetic disease, genetic condition, etc

Narrow synonym: Mendelian disease

We typically have not represented monogenic diseases with a few exceptions:

- 'monogenic alpha thalassemia spectrum'
- 'monogenic diabetes'
- 'monogenic epilepsy'

Recap: Previous discussions on hereditary and monogenic disease

From Chris: The central question was:

1. does it make sense to differentiate between monogenic and digenic via grouping classes in the ontology?
 - a. *Note, we later obsoleted 'monogenic disease' and added consider: hereditary disease (MONDO:0003847)*
2. if so, how do we ensure the ontology stays up to date with current findings

On (2): don't think this is easy to tell from existing gene to disease resources. It can be hard to tell computationally if cardinality>1 is to be interpreted as a can-be-caused-by-either-of or digenic.

Chris is convinced that as a group we can solve this problem, but I don't think this will happen overnight. He is concerned that in the short term we don't put out misleading incomplete information, or incorrect information. If you put a term in an ontology, you are committed to doing a good job of fully populating it, within reason, otherwise users will be confused.

It seems safer to roll up to whatever we call the grouping class of mono/di for now, and return to this later. But he may be overestimating the curation effort

[Melissa said](#): idea was to obsolete and have monogenic/polygenic be inferred from the annotations

Etiology

Structural

Genetic

Infectious

Metabolic

Immune

Unknown

- Currently in Mondo (as of our new revisions), we now have:
 - 'genetic generalized epilepsy' in the 'epilepsy/generalized epilepsy' branch
 - 'monogenic epilepsy' in the main 'epilepsy' branch
- See proposal next slide

Proposed genetic epilepsy hierarchy

Proposal:

- New classes in blue
- The classes in white represent the diseases which will be represented, but we will not create grouping classes for these.
- Eg, we will not create a grouping class for "non-hereditary", but we would have diseases that are due to de novo mutations that will be siblings to hereditary.

How would you (experts) recommend classifying genetic epilepsies/how would you expect to see them classified?

Epilepsy Syndromes

Epilepsy syndrome is currently undefined in Mondo.

How do we define epilepsy syndrome? Should epilepsy be a major feature? Or should epilepsy be one of the features?

Proposal: add ILAE definition? Or revised definition?

From ILAE: An epilepsy syndrome is defined when there is a characteristic cluster of clinical and EEG features, that are often supported by specific etiological findings (structural, genetic, metabolic, immune and infectious). The diagnosis of a syndrome in an individual with epilepsy frequently carries prognostic and treatment implications. Syndromes often have age-dependent presentations and a range of specific comorbidities.

The identification of a syndrome is useful as it provides information on which underlying etiologies should be considered. Several syndromes demonstrate seizure aggravation with particular medications, which can be avoided with early diagnosis of the syndrome.

Epilepsy syndromes can be grouped by age of seizure onset and by epilepsy type. Some epilepsy syndromes are self-limited, others are associated with enduring epilepsy. Some are associated with **encephalopathy** and others are not.

Etiology-specific epilepsy syndromes are a work in progress, a definition can be found at link [here](#).

- The terms in orange are in Mondo and in the current ILAE classification
- What to do with the other terms classified under 'epilepsy syndrome'?

- ▼ ● epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0015650)
 - 'adolescent-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020073)
 - 'adolescent/adult-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100030)
 - 'childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020072)
 - 'epileptic encephalopathy, infantile or early childhood' (MONDO:0020627)
 - 'infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020071)
 - 'Moynahan syndrome' (MONDO:0008755)
 - 'neonatal epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020070)
 - 'neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100022)
 - variable-age onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100036)

*Let's dive in to
epilepsy syndromes -
starting with the
grouping terms in
ILAE*

- The terms in orange are in the current ILAE classification
- What to do with the other terms classified under 'epilepsy syndrome'?

- ▼ ● epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0020627)
 - 'adolescent-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020627)
 - 'adolescent/adult-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100030)
 - 'benign occipital epilepsy' (MONDO:0020627)
 - 'childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020627)
 - 'epileptic encephalopathy' (MONDO:0020627)
 - 'infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020071)
 - 'Moynahan syndrome' (MONDO:0008755)
 - 'neonatal epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020070)
 - 'neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100022)
 - variable-age onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100036)

- **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0020072)**
 - **childhood-onset self-limited focal epilepsy syndrome**
 - **childhood-onset genetic generalized epilepsy syndrome**
 - **childhood-onset idiopathic generalized epilepsy syndrome**
 - **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy**

Mondo classification

We don't have any of the ILAE terms under childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome, do we need these grouping classes?

In the next slide, we expand the hierarchy and look at what we do have in Mondo

- **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0020072)**
 - **childhood-onset self-limited focal epilepsy syndrome**
 - **Remission expected in all cases by adolescence**
 - **self-limited epilepsy with centrotemporal spikes (SeLECTS)**
 - **self-limited epilepsy with autonomic seizures (SeLEAS) (MONDO:0020307)**
 - **Remission expected in most cases by adolescence**
 - **childhood occipital visual epilepsy (MONDO:0020308)**
 - **photosensitive occipital lobe epilepsy (MONDO:0100021)**
 - **childhood-onset genetic generalized epilepsy syndrome**
 - **epilepsy with eyelid myoclonia (EEM) (MONDO:0015346)**
 - **epilepsy with myoclonic absences (MONDO:0019487)**
 - **childhood-onset idiopathic generalized epilepsy syndrome**
 - **childhood absence epilepsy (MONDO:0010826)**
 - **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy**
 - **epilepsy with myoclonic atonic seizures (MONDO:0016025) *question below (2 slides)**
 - **Lennox-Gastaut syndrome (MONDO:0016532)**
 - **developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy with spike-wave activation in sleep**
 - **febrile infection-related epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0015584)**
 - **hemiconvulsion-hemiplegia-epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0019485)**

Legend:

Terms are in Mondo
Propose adding term
to Mondo

- childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0020072)

- **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome**
 - ★ ● acute encephalopathy with biphasic seizures and late reduced diffusion
 - ★ ● atypical childhood epilepsy with centrotemporal spikes
 - childhood absence epilepsy
 - cryptogenic late-onset epileptic spasms
 - ★ ● early-onset epileptic encephalopathy and intellectual disability due to GRIN2A mutation
 - epilepsy with eyelid myoclonia
 - epilepsy with myoclonic absences
 - ★ ● familial partial epilepsy
 - febrile infection-related epilepsy syndrome
 - idiopathic hemiconvulsion
 - ★ ● Landau-Kleffner syndrome
 - Lennox-Gastaut syndrome
 - myoclonic-astatic epilepsy
 - new-onset refractory status epilepticus
 - perioral myoclonia with absences
 - ★ ● photosensitive occipital lobe epilepsy
 - ★ ● progressive myoclonus epilepsy
 - rolandic epilepsy-paroxysmal exercise-induced dystonia-writer's cramp syndrome
 - rolandic epilepsy-speech dyspraxia syndrome
 - ★ ● self-limited childhood occipital epilepsy
 - ★ ● Sunflower syndrome
 - epileptic encephalopathy, infantile or early childhood

id:
are in Mondo
se adding term
ndo

There are a lot of classes classified under 'childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome' in Mondo that are not in ILAE (★). I propose that we revisit these after we revise the hierarchy according to ILAE

1 in sleep

Preferred label (ILAE): **epilepsy with myoclonic atonic seizures**

ILAE Definition:

Epilepsy with myoclonic atonic seizures (previously known as Doose syndrome) is a syndrome characterized by the usually abrupt onset of multiple generalized seizure types, including myoclonic-atonic seizures in early childhood. Developmental stagnation or regression is typically seen during the phase of active seizures. Despite initial drug-resistant seizures, two thirds of children achieve epilepsy remission.

Synonym: EMAtS

Question: is 'myoclonic-astatic epilepsy' the same as 'myoclonic-atonic epilepsy'? (ie should these two terms be merged?)

myoclonic-astatic epilepsy is not in ILAE

Definition: A rare, childhood onset epilepsy syndrome characterized by multiple seizure types including myoclonic-atonic (MA) seizures that occur usually in previously healthy children. (Orphanet:1942)

synonym: "**Doose syndrome**" EXACT [GARD:0002169, Orphanet:1942]

synonym: "**epilepsy with myoclonic atonic seizures**" EXACT [PMID:37498137]

synonym: "**epilepsy with myoclonic-astatic seizures**" EXACT [GARD:0002169, Orphanet:1942]

synonym: "**epilepsy with myoclonic-atonic seizures**" EXACT [Orphanet:1942]

synonym: "MAE" RELATED ABBREVIATION [Orphanet:1942]

synonym: "**myoclonic atonic epilepsy**" EXACT [Orphanet:1942]

Partial list of synonyms is included above to highlight the overlap with the 'myoclonic-atonic epilepsy' term

'myoclonic-atonic epilepsy'

Definition: An idiopathic generalized epilepsy characterized by onset of multiple seizure types in the first few years of life and associated with poor prognosis. Affected individuals have cognitive regression and intellectual disability and that has material basis in heterozygous mutation in the SLC6A1 gene on chromosome 3p25. (DOID:0060475)

synonym: "MAE" EXACT ABBREVIATION [MONDO:Lexical, OMIM:616421]

synonym: "Myoclonic Atonic Epilepsy" EXACT [NORD:2035]

synonym: "myoclonic-atonic epilepsy" EXACT [MONDO:Lexical, OMIM:616421]

- According to ILAE, this is not a subtype of 'idiopathic generalized epilepsy'

- **neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100022)**
 - **neonatal/infantile-onset self-limited epilepsy syndrome**
 - **neonatal/infantile-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and epileptic encephalopathy**

Mondo classification

Question:

- 1) We have both neonatal epilepsy syndrome and neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome - these seem like they should be combined?
- 2) Do we want to add these grouping classes from ILAE?

- **neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100022)**
 - **neonatal/infantile-onset self-limited epilepsy syndrome**
 - **self-limited (familial) neonatal epilepsy (MONDO:0800479)**
 - **self-limited familial neonatal-infantile epilepsy (MONDO:0100208)**
 - **self-limited (familial) infantile epilepsy (MONDO:0100024)**
 - **genetic epilepsy with febrile seizures plus spectrum**
 - **myoclonic epilepsy in infancy (MONDO:0100566)**
 - **neonatal/infantile-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and epileptic encephalopathy** ***There are a lot of open questions about this branch in the slides below**
 - **early-infantile DEE**
 - **epilepsy of infancy with migrating focal seizures (MONDO:0100025)**
 - **infantile epileptic spasms syndrome (MONDO:0018097)**
 - **Dravet syndrome (MONDO:0100135)**

Legend:

Terms are in Mondo
Propose adding term
to Mondo

Question:

Should we group these terms this way and create new grouping classes and new terms?

Proposal:

- 'variable age onset epilepsy' should be reclassified under 'epilepsy syndrome'
- Rename to 'variable age onset epilepsy syndrome'

Question:

Should we group the terms this way and add new terms?

- **variable-age onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100036)**
 - **variable-age onset idiopathic generalized epilepsy syndrome**
 - **juvenile myoclonic epilepsy (MONDO:0009696)**
 - **juvenile absence epilepsy (MONDO:0800453)**
 - **epilepsy with generalized tonic-clonic seizures alone (MONDO:0005754)**
 - **variable-age onset focal epilepsy syndrome**
 - **sleep-related hypermotor (hyperkinetic) epilepsy (MONDO:0000030)**
 - **familial mesial temporal lobe epilepsy**
 - **epilepsy with auditory features *see slide below**
 - **familial focal epilepsy with variable foci (MONDO:0020310)**
 - **variable-age onset combined generalized and focal epilepsy syndromes**
 - **epilepsy with reading-induced seizures (MONDO:0007560)**
 - **variable age epilepsy syndrome with developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy or progressive neurological deterioration**
 - **progressive myoclonus epilepsy (MONDO:0020074)**
 - **Rasmussen syndrome (MONDO:0016019)**

Proposal: add 'variable-age onset focal epilepsy syndrome' as a new term

- **Add child class:**

- 'epilepsy with auditory features' as child of 'variable-age onset focal epilepsy syndrome' per ILAE
- **Definition:** Epilepsy with auditory features (EAF) is a focal epilepsy syndrome with characteristic focal aware sensory auditory seizures. Seizures often produce such mild symptoms that they are not diagnosed. There are no implications expected for development or learning and seizures are typically infrequent and well controlled. EAF may occur as a familial syndrome, familial EAF (FEAF, previous known as autosomal dominant lateral temporal lobe epilepsy or autosomal dominant partial epilepsy with auditory features). Inheritance may be autosomal dominant (ADEAF), with incomplete penetrance.

- **Proposal:** Merge 'autosomal dominant epilepsy with auditory features' and 'adolescent/adult onset autosomal dominant epilepsy with auditory features' - the latter is from ILAE only and seems to be the same term and this naming convention seems to be no longer used in ILAE. (Note - ILAE says: This syndrome *typically* has onset between 10-30 years (range 0.5-54 years).

End of Part 2

mondo

THE WORLD'S DISEASE CONCEPTS, UNIFIED

Epilepsy Workshop Part 3: January 17, 2025

Your facilitators

Nicole Vasilevsky

Associate Director of Data Science
DCC, Critical Path Institute

Sabrina Toro

Lead Biocurator
TISLab, University of North Carolina

Welcome!

Time	Agenda Item
8:00 AM PT / 11:00 AM ET	Welcome, logistics and code of conduct
8:10 AM PT / 11:05 AM ET	Introduce attendees
8:15 AM PT / 11:15 AM PT	Epilepsy classification top level classification + questions about terms of interest
9:50 AM PT / 12:50 PM ET	Adjournment

WORKSHOP GOALS

1

Upper level classification of epilepsy disease branch/alignment with ILAE

2

Review classification and definitions of key terms of interest

3

Future: Write a community-based manuscript describing the outcomes of these workshops

Introductions

ILAE high level classifications

Workshop outcomes by the numbers (so far...)

346

Epilepsy
disease
terms

23

New terms added

New Classifications in Specific Areas:

Immune
epilepsy

Genetic
epilepsy

Generalized
epilepsy

Epilepsy
syndrome

3 proposed term
mergers (2 done)

6 proposed term
obsoletions (1
done)

ILAE high level classifications

Last time we reviewed the terms in Mondo and updated the children per ILAE

- ▼ ● epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0015650)
 - 'adolescent-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020073)
 - 'adolescent/adult-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100030)
 - 'childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020072)
 - 'epileptic encephalopathy, infantile or early childhood' (MONDO:0020627)
 - 'infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020071)
 - 'Moynahan syndrome' (MONDO:0008755)
 - 'neonatal epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020070)
 - 'neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100022)
 - 'variable-age onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100036)

We implemented some changes to the branches in orange

We'll go through these one by one in the slides below

New Changes Implemented (per Workshop Part 2)

- **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0020072)**
 - **childhood-onset self-limited focal epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0800496)**
 - **self-limited epilepsy with centrotemporal spikes (SeLECTS) (MONDO:0007295)**
 - **self-limited epilepsy with autonomic seizures (SeLEAS) (MONDO:0020307)**
 - **childhood occipital visual epilepsy (MONDO:0020308)**
 - **photosensitive occipital lobe epilepsy (MONDO:0100021)**
 - **childhood-onset genetic generalized epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0800498)**
 - **epilepsy with eyelid myoclonia (EEM) (MONDO:0015346)**
 - **epilepsy with myoclonic absences (MONDO:0019487)**
 - **childhood-onset idiopathic generalized epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0800499)**
 - **childhood absence epilepsy (MONDO:0010826)**
 - **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy (MONDO:0800500)**
 - **epilepsy with myoclonic atonic seizures (MONDO:0014633)**
 - **Lennox-Gastaut syndrome (MONDO:0016532)**
 - **developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy with spike-wave activation in sleep (MONDO:0800501)**
 - **febrile infection-related epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0015584)**
 - **hemiconvulsion-hemiplegia-epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0019485)**

Legend:
 Terms are in
 Mondo
 New terms
 added to
 Mondo

New Changes Implemented (per Workshop Part 2)

- **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0020072)**
 - **childhood-onset self-limited focal epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0800496)**
 - **self-limited epilepsy with centrotemporal spikes (SeLECTS) (MONDO:0007295)**
 - **self-limited epilepsy with autonomic seizures (SeLEAS) (MONDO:0020307)**
 - **childhood occipital visual epilepsy (MONDO:0020308)**
 - **photosensitive occipital lobe epilepsy (MONDO:0100021)**
 - **childhood-onset genetic generalized epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0800498)**
 - **epilepsy with eyelid myoclonia (EEM) (MONDO:0015346)**
 - **epilepsy with myoclonic absences (MONDO:0019487)**
 - **childhood-onset idiopathic generalized epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0800499)**
 - **childhood absence epilepsy (MONDO:0010826)**
 - **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy (MONDO:0800500)**
 - **epilepsy with myoclonic atonic seizures (MONDO:0014633)**
 - **Lennox-Gastaut syndrome (MONDO:0016532)**
 - **developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy with spike-wave activation in sleep (MONDO:0800501)**
 - **febrile infection-related epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0015584)**
 - **hemiconvulsion-hemiplegia-epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0019485)**

Legend:
Terms are in
Mondo
New terms
added to
Mondo

New Changes Implemented (per Workshop Part 2)

- **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0020072)**
 - **childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy (MONDO:0800500)**
 - **myoclonic-atic epilepsy (syn: epilepsy with myoclonic atonic seizures (MONDO:0014633))**
 - **Lennox-Gastaut syndrome (MONDO:0016532)**
 - **developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy with spike-wave activation in sleep (MONDO:0800501)**
 - **febrile infection-related epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0015584)**
 - **hemiconvulsion-hemiplegia-epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0019485)**

Legend:
Terms are in Mondo
New terms added to Mondo

Terms were merged:

New Changes Implemented (per Workshop Part 2)

- **neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100022)**
 - **neonatal/infantile-onset self-limited epilepsy syndrome**
 - **self-limited (familial) neonatal epilepsy (MONDO:0800479)**
 - **self-limited familial neonatal-infantile epilepsy (MONDO:0100208)**
 - **self-limited (familial) infantile epilepsy (MONDO:0100024)**
 - **genetic epilepsy with febrile seizures plus spectrum**
 - **myoclonic epilepsy in infancy (MONDO:0100566)**
 - **neonatal/infantile-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and epileptic encephalopathy**
 - **early-infantile DEE**
 - **epilepsy of infancy with migrating focal seizures (MONDO:0100025)**
 - **infantile epileptic spasms syndrome (MONDO:0018097)**
 - **Dravet syndrome (MONDO:0100135)**

Legend:

Terms are in Mondo
New terms added to Mondo

New Changes Implemented (per Workshop Part 2)

- **variable-age onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100036)**
 - **variable-age onset idiopathic generalized epilepsy syndrome**
 - **juvenile myoclonic epilepsy (MONDO:0009696)**
 - **juvenile absence epilepsy (MONDO:0800453)**
 - **epilepsy with generalized tonic-clonic seizures alone (MONDO:0005754)**
 - **variable-age onset focal epilepsy syndrome**
 - **sleep-related hypermotor (hyperkinetic) epilepsy (MONDO:0000030)**
 - **familial mesial temporal lobe epilepsy**
 - **epilepsy with auditory features**
 - **familial focal epilepsy with variable foci (MONDO:0020310)**
 - **variable-age onset combined generalized and focal epilepsy syndromes**
 - **epilepsy with reading-induced seizures (MONDO:0007560)**
 - **variable age epilepsy syndrome with developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy or progressive neurological deterioration**
 - **progressive myoclonus epilepsy (MONDO:0020074)**
 - **Rasmussen syndrome (MONDO:0016019)**

Legend:

Terms are in Mondo
New terms added to Mondo

Relationship between epilepsy and 'epilepsy syndrome'

Specific epilepsy syndrome terms are children of 'epilepsy syndrome' and specific epilepsy terms

Today we'll focus on Mondo terms that are not in ILAE (black text)

- ▼ ● epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0015650)
 - 'adolescent-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020073)
 - 'adolescent/adult-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100030)
 - 'childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020072)
 - 'epileptic encephalopathy, infantile or early childhood' (MONDO:0020627)
 - 'infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020071)
 - 'Moynahan syndrome' (MONDO:0008755)
 - 'neonatal epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020070)
 - 'neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100022)
 - variable-age onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100036)

We'll go through these one by one in the slides below

'adolescent-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020073)

Comment (on term): This type of grouping class represents an older way of classifying diseases, and represented here

<https://www.epilepsydiagnosis.org/index.html>

Note: This term is no longer in ILAE

Proposal:

- Obsolete this grouping class and reclassify children as subtypes of epilepsy syndrome (if they are not already classified elsewhere)

'adolescent/adult-onset epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100030)

Comment (on term): This type of grouping class represents an older way of classifying diseases, and represented here <https://www.epilepsydiagnosis.org/index.html>. Reason of obsolescence: out of scope - MONDO:excludeHistoricalDisease. Term to consider: -

Note: This term is no longer in ILAE

Proposal:

- Proceed with obsolescence of this grouping class
- The subclasses already are classified elsewhere

'epileptic encephalopathy, infantile or early childhood' (MONDO:0020627)

-
- epilepsy syndrome
 - adolescent-onset epilepsy syndrome
 - adolescent/adult-onset epilepsy syndrome
 - ≡ childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome
 - **epileptic encephalopathy, infantile or early childhood**
 - ≡ infantile epilepsy syndrome
 - Moynahan syndrome
 - ≡ neonatal epilepsy syndrome
 - neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome

Note: This term is no longer in OMIM

Proposal:

- We should obsolete this class

'infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020071)

- ☰ infantile epilepsy syndrome
 - ★ ● benign partial infantile seizures
 - idiopathic hemiconvulsion-hemiplegia syndrome
 - ★ ● infantile epilepsy with migrant focal crisis
 - infantile spasms-broad thumbs syndrome
 - ★ ● infantile-onset mesial temporal lobe epilepsy with severe cognitive regression
 - ★ ● myoclonic epilepsy in non-progressive encephalopathies
 - ★ ● progressive myoclonic epilepsy with dystonia
 - ★ ● SYNGAP1-related developmental and epileptic encephalopathy
 - ★ ● undetermined early-onset epileptic encephalopathy

Comment (on term): This type of grouping class represents an older way of classifying diseases, and represented here

<https://www.epilepsydiagnosis.org/index.html>

Note: This term is no longer in ILAE but it is used in Orphanet to group a number of terms (indicated with a ★)

Question:

Should we keep this based on Orphanet's usage or Obsolete because ILAE does not use it and reclassify children as subtypes of neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome?

'infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020071)

'neonatal epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020070)

'neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100022)

Proposal:

Merge 'infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020071) and 'neonatal epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020070) into 'neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0100022)

'self-limited (familial) neonatal seizures' (MONDO:0800479)

vs 'self-limited familial neonatal epilepsy' (MONDO:0100023)

- Do we need a syndromic form and non-syndromic form of the terms above?
- ClinGen asked for the creation of 'infantile-onset epilepsy' that differs from 'infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020071), as there are forms of this disease that do not have a syndromic presentation
- They noted that the Epilepsy Gene Curation Expert Panel wants to be cognizant of the difference between syndromic and non-syndromic disease terms, and these terms do not appear to necessitate syndromic presentation

Question:

Should we align with ILAE or ClinGen or both and have two terms?

See diagram, next slide

ClinGen
ILAE
In ILAE but not in Mondo

Question:

Should we align with ILAE or ClinGen or both and have two terms?

ClinGen
ILAE
In ILAE but not in Mondo

Question:
Should we align with ILAE or ClinGen or both and have two terms?

Should the syndromic type be a child of the non-syndromic type?

→

'Moynahan syndrome' (MONDO:0008755)

- epilepsy syndrome
 - adolescent-onset epilepsy syndrome
 - adolescent/adult-onset epilepsy syndrome
 - ≡ childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome
 - epileptic encephalopathy, infantile or early childhood
 - ≡ infantile epilepsy syndrome
 - **Moynahan syndrome**
 - ≡ neonatal epilepsy syndrome
 - neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome

Note: Epilepsy is a feature of this disease (classification comes from Orphanet)

Proposal:
Reclassify this term as a Mendelian disease

Syndromic epilepsies

MONDO:0008045

spinal muscular atrophy-progressive myoclonic epilepsy syndrome

- Should this be a child of:
 - Syndromic disease
- or
- Spinal muscular atrophy *and*
- Myoclonic epilepsy

This is grouping a syndromic term based on features (which we don't normally do)

<https://github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo/issues/5655>

Current parents

SubClass Of

- **Note:** we do not have **myoclonic epilepsy** in Mondo
- We have:
 - MONDO:0100566 'myoclonic epilepsy in infancy'
 - MONDO:0009696 'juvenile myoclonic epilepsy'
 - MONDO:0000160 'epilepsy, familial adult myoclonic'
- *Do we need this grouping class? (This question comes up again below)*

'autosomal recessive cerebellar ataxia - epilepsy - intellectual disability syndrome'

- **Related example:**
 - 'Autosomal recessive cerebellar ataxia - epilepsy - intellectual disability syndrome' is classified as a 'monogenic epilepsy' per Orphanet and 'autosomal recessive cerebellar ataxia' (per Orphanet)
 - The subclasses are labeled differently in Orphanet:
 - Autosomal recessive spinocerebellar ataxia 12 (OMIM) = Autosomal recessive cerebellar ataxia-epilepsy-intellectual disability syndrome due to WWOX deficiency (Orphanet)
- *Should these be children of 'monogenic epilepsy'?*

WORKSHOP GOALS

1

Review how to contribute to the Mondo disease ontology using GitHub

2

Upper level classification of epilepsy disease branch/alignment with ILAE

3

Review classification and definitions of key terms of interest

4

(Time allowing) Review classification of terms as diseases and/or phenotypes

5

Build collaborations and strengthen the community with experts in the field

DEEs

Developmental and epileptic encephalopathy

- Child of
 - neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome
 - complex neurodevelopmental disorder
 - Mendelian neurodevelopmental disorder (inferred)

- In the Part 1 workshop, attendees said this should not be a Mendelian disease
- DEE is an OMIM phenotypic series, which is always ‘inherited’

Proposal:

- Create a new generic DEE class
 - Child of ‘complex neurodevelopmental disorder’? And/or epilepsy?
- Rename DEE (MONDO:0100062) to ‘hereditary DEE’
 - Child of generic DEE

Developmental and epileptic encephalopathy

- “It is therefore suggested that the term “developmental and epileptic encephalopathy” be used where appropriate and can be applied to individuals of any age.”

(<https://www.ilae.org/index.cfm?objectid=35BBF2E0-22F2-11E8-99F2141877632E8F>)

Proposal:

DEE should not be a child of neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome

Developmental and epileptic encephalopathy: New proposed hierarchy

Children of DEE (currently in Mondo)

- There are the numbered DEEs from OMIM (correspond to particular gene variations)
- **Dravet syndrome** was requested to be a child of DEE per ClinGen Epilepsy Gene Curation Expert Panel: <https://github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo/issues/745>

See next slide

Dravet syndrome

- **Dravet syndrome** was requested to be a child of DEE per ClinGen Epilepsy Gene Curation Expert Panel: <https://github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo/issues/745>
- ILAE classifies it under 'neonatal/infantile-onset epilepsy syndrome with DEE'

New revisions:

- Created new class (light blue)
- Added Dravet Syndrome as a child of this
- Created 'early-infantile DEE'

Children of DEE (currently in Mondo)

'hemiplegic migraine-developmental and epileptic encephalopathy spectrum'

was requested to be a child of DEE per ClinGen Epilepsy Gene Curation Expert

Panel: <https://github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo/issues/7195>

No action needed

Subclass of DEE (currently in Mondo)

developmental and epileptic encephalopathy

- 'Lennox-Gastaut syndrome' was requested to be a child of DEE per Pirrette Lo (and discussion with an expert): <https://github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo/issues/5350>
- In ILAE, LGS is a subclass of 'childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0020072)/childhood-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and/or epileptic encephalopathy (MONDO:0800500) - this was recently added (and LGS is a child)

Question:

Should LGS be a child of the generic DEE?

It is not always genetic, correct?

Subclass of DEE (currently in Mondo)

'microcephaly, seizures, and developmental delay' is classified as a DEE per OMIM

No action needed

Subclass of DEE (currently in Mondo)

'multiple congenital anomalies-hypotonia-seizures syndrome 2' is classified as a DEE per OMIM

No action needed

Subclass of DEE (currently in Mondo)

'neonatal-onset developmental and epileptic encephalopathy' is classified as a DEE per ClinGen Epilepsy Gene Curation Expert Panel:

<https://github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo/issues/4058>

No action needed

Subclass of DEE (currently in Mondo)

'**neonatal-onset encephalopathy with rigidity and seizures**' is classified as a DEE per ClinGen Epilepsy Gene Curation Expert Panel:

<https://github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo/issues/5125>

No action needed

Subclass of DEE (currently in Mondo)

'**non-neonatal early infantile epileptic encephalopathy**' is classified as a DEE per ClinGen Epilepsy Gene Curation Expert Panel, but it tagged for obsolescence.

No action needed

Revisiting the neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome branch...

- **neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100022)**
 - **neonatal/infantile-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and epileptic encephalopathy (MONDO:0800490)**
 - **early-infantile DEE (MONDO:0800491)**
 - **epilepsy of infancy with migrating focal seizures (MONDO:0100025)**
 - **infantile epileptic spasms syndrome (MONDO:0018097)**
 - **Dravet syndrome (MONDO:0100135)**

Legend:

Terms are in Mondo
Propose adding term
to Mondo

Proposal: Add superclass generic DEE

early infantile DEE

Definition: A neonatal/infantile-onset epilepsy syndrome characterized by frequent drug-resistant seizures that begin ≤ 3 months of age, with abnormal interictal EEG and neurological examination. This syndrome encompasses the previous syndromes of Ohtahara syndrome and **early myoclonic encephalopathy**. Treatable metabolic etiologies (especially pyridoxine and pyridoxal-5-phosphate disorders) should be excluded early.

Parent: **generic DEE (MONDO:0800491)** and **neonatal/infantile-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and epileptic encephalopathy (MONDO:0800490)**

Merge? 'early myoclonic encephalopathy' (MONDO:0016022) into 'early infantile DEE' (see next slide)

Proposed changes to DEE

Proposal:
Reclassify early infantile DEE
Parent: generic DEE (new term) and
"neonatal/infantile-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and epileptic encephalopathy" (MONDO:0800490)

Merge 'early myoclonic encephalopathy' (MONDO:0016022) into 'early infantile DEE'

Reclassify(?) two of the children that are currently children of 'early myoclonic encephalopathy' (highlighted in yellow) - see next slide

What to do about these myoclonic epilepsy classes?

Proposal:

Merge 'early myoclonic encephalopathy' (MONDO:0016022) into 'early infantile DEE'

Questions:

- How should the two classes below (highlighted in yellow) be (re)classified? Does it make sense for them to be a child of early-DEE or should they be reclassified?
- One has another parent, but the other does not
- Would it make sense to create a new '**myoclonic epilepsy**' grouping term?

And what about 'myoclonic epilepsy, Hartung type'?

- **Is this a legitimate disease?**
- Only 2 papers and the last one is from 1965
- Should we keep it for legacy purposes?

<https://omim.org/entry/159600>

% 159600

MYOCLONIC EPILEPSY, HARTUNG TYPE

Clinical Synopsis ▾

▼ TEXT

This form appears to be distinct from the two types that are inherited as autosomal recessives (254780, 254800). Unlike those forms, no Lafora bodies were found at autopsy and only diffuse atrophy was present.

▼ See Also:

[Hartung \(1920\)](#); [Vogel et al. \(1965\)](#)

▼ REFERENCES

1. Hartung, E. **Zwei Faelle von Paramyoclonus multiplex mit Epilepsie.** Z. Ges. Neurol. Psychiat. 56: 150-153, 1920.
2. Vogel, F., Hafner, H., Diebold, K. **Zur Genetik der progressiven Myoklonusepilepsien (Unverricht-Lundborg).** Humangenetik 1: 437-475, 1965. [PubMed: [5868699](#), [related citations](#)]

Proposed changes to Ohtahara syndrome

“Early-infantile developmental and epileptic encephalopathy syndrome (EIDEE) ... **encompasses the previous syndromes of Ohtahara syndrome** and early myoclonic encephalopathy...”

Proposal:

Move synonym for Ohtahara syndrome to ‘early-infantile DEE’ per ILAE

Revisiting the neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome branch...

- **neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome (MONDO:0100022)**
 - **neonatal/infantile-onset epilepsy syndrome with developmental and epileptic encephalopathy**
 - **early-infantile DEE**
 - **epilepsy of infancy with migrating focal seizures (MONDO:0100025)**
 - ★ **infantile epileptic spasms syndrome (MONDO:0018097)**
 - **Dravet syndrome (MONDO:0100135)**

Legend:

Terms are in Mondo
Propose adding term
to Mondo

**Focus on 'infantile epileptic spasms
syndrome - next slide**

'West syndrome' (MONDO:0018097)

From ILAE: Infantile epileptic spasms syndrome is characterized by the onset of epileptic spasms in the infant (age 1-24 months). This syndrome includes West syndrome, where patients have a triad of epileptic spasms, hypsarrhythmia on EEG and developmental plateauing or regression.

Proposal:

New term: infantile epileptic spasms syndrome
Synonym: IESS

Subclass:

West syndrome

Def: An infantile epileptic spasms syndrome that is characterized by a triad of epileptic spasms, hypsarrhythmia on EEG and developmental plateauing or regression.

Disease vs Phenotype

'status epilepticus' (MONDO:0002125)

Definition: A life-threatening situation in which the brain is in a continuous state of seizure.

'status epilepticus' (HP:0002133)

Definition: Status epilepticus is a type of prolonged seizure resulting either from the failure of the mechanisms responsible for seizure termination or from the initiation of mechanisms which lead to abnormally prolonged seizures (after time point t1). It is a condition that can have long-term consequences (after time point t2), including neuronal death, neuronal injury, and alteration of neuronal networks, depending on the type and duration of seizures.

Is 'status epilepticus' a disease?

AI Overview

Yes, status epilepticus is considered a medical condition or a neurological disorder, often classified as a life-threatening emergency, rather than just a symptom; it refers to a prolonged seizure or series of seizures without regaining consciousness, essentially an acute exacerbation of epilepsy or a seizure disorder that requires immediate medical attention.

Key points about status epilepticus:

Definition:

A state where seizures last for an extended period (typically over 5 minutes) or occur repeatedly without regaining consciousness between episodes.

Severity:

Considered a medical emergency due to the potential for brain damage and even death if not treated promptly.

Causes:

Can be triggered by various factors including changes in epilepsy medication, infections, head injuries, metabolic imbalances, drug withdrawal, or even as the initial presentation of epilepsy.

Treatment:

Requires immediate medical intervention with medications to stop the seizures, often

Learn more

Status Epilepticus: What It Is, Causes, Symptoms & Treatment

Feb 13, 2023 — Status epilepticus is a dangerous brain condition that happens when a person has seizures that last t...

Cleveland Clinic

Status Epilepticus - Medscape Reference

Jan 7, 2021 — Status epilepticus (SE) is a common, life-threatening neurologic disorder. It is essentially an acute,...

Medscape Reference

What is status epilepticus and what do we know about its ...

A disease is not easy to define. The issue has been recently raised, in relation to regulatory approval of novel therapies, a...

ScienceDirect.com

Show all

'epilepsia partialis continua' (MONDO:0006748)

Definition: A variant of epilepsy characterized by continuous focal jerking of a body part over a period of hours, days, or even years without spreading to other body regions. Contractions may be aggravated by movement and are reduced, but not abolished during sleep. electroencephalography demonstrates epileptiform (spike and wave) discharges over the hemisphere opposite to the affected limb in most instances. The repetitive movements may originate from the cerebral cortex or from subcortical structures (e.g., brain stem; basal ganglia). This condition is associated with Russian Spring and Summer encephalitis; Rasmussen syndrome; multiple sclerosis; diabetes mellitus; brain neoplasms; and cerebrovascular disorders

'epilepsia partialis continua' (HP:0002133)

Definition: Epilepsia partialis continua (also called Kojevnikov's or Kozhevnikov's epilepsy) is a type of focal motor status epilepticus characterized by repeated stereotyped simple motor manifestations such as jerks, typically of a limb or the face, recurring every few seconds or minutes for extended periods (days or years).

Is 'epilepsia
partialis
continua'
a disease?

- Is a type of status epilepticus, if we keep that, then this should be a subclass? (Currently is a subclass of epilepsy)
- Deprecated in DO (DOID:11349)

**THAT'S
ALL**

Next steps

- **Implement remaining changes in Mondo**
 - Create GitHub issues for changes we discussed today
 - May have further discussions as needed
 - Implement changes we discussed today
 - Changes will be available in future release (releases are first Tuesday of each month)
- **Community-authored manuscript**
 - We'll aim to write/share a summary of Part 2 before the end of the year
 - We will follow up to collect authorship information
 - Will share an [outline/draft of the paper](#) in upcoming months
- **Solicit additional community feedback via feedback form**

Thank you!

mondo

THE WORLD'S DISEASE CONCEPTS, UNIFIED

Slides under
development

Unused slides

Legend

- ★ New term added
- ★ Relabel and reclassification
- ★ Reclassification

ORIGINAL HIERARCHY

- epilepsy
 - autoimmune epilepsy
 - electroclinical syndrome
 - epilepsy partialis continua
 - epilepsy syndrome
 - epilepsy, idiopathic generalized
 - extratemporal epilepsy
 - focal epilepsy
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus
 - immune epilepsy
 - infantile-onset epilepsy
 - metabolic epilepsy
 - monogenic epilepsy
 - post-traumatic epilepsy
 - status epilepticus
 - structural epilepsy

NEW REVISIONS

- focal epilepsy
 - combined generalized and focal epilepsy
 - complex partial epilepsy
 - familial partial epilepsy
 - frontal lobe epilepsy
 - partial motor epilepsy
 - partial sensory epilepsy
 - simple partial epilepsy
- ★ ● generalized epilepsy
 - combined generalized and focal epilepsy
 - ★ ● juvenile myoclonic epilepsy
 - myoclonic epilepsy, juvenile, 2
 - ★ ● genetic generalized epilepsy
 - ★ ● hereditary generalized epilepsy
 - ★ ● generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus
 - febrile seizures, familial, 8
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 1
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 10
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 12
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 2
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 4
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 6
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 7
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 8
 - generalized epilepsy with febrile seizures plus, type 9
 - ★ ● idiopathic generalized epilepsy
 - ★ ● childhood absence epilepsy
 - ★ ● epilepsy with generalized tonic-clonic seizures
 - ★ ● juvenile absence epilepsy
 - ★ ● juvenile myoclonic epilepsy

MONDO:0005027
Epilepsy

MONDO:0100574
**generalized
epilepsy**

New term?
epilepsy, unknown type

MONDO:0017704
familial partial epilepsy

MONDO:0100033
metabolic epilepsy

MONDO:0011891
**febrile seizures,
familial, 8**

MONDO:0019197
**folinic acid-responsive
seizures**

Human Phenotype Ontology

Approx. 14,000 phenotype terms

Am J Hum Genet 2008
Am J Hum Genet 2009
Nucl Acids Res 2014
Nucl Acids Res 2017
Nat Genet 2018

Mondo Stats (old)

22,157 disease terms

104,479
Database cross reference

15,443
Term definitions

66,247 Exact synonyms

2,214 Narrow synonyms

30,661 Related synonyms

847 Broad synonyms

10,443

Rare diseases

1,240

Infectious diseases

4,298

Cancers (including neoplasms)

11,380

Mendelian diseases

Epilepsy classification in Mondo: Focus on upper level classification

We have a mix of epilepsy types, etiology and other classifications

'infantile epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020071)

- ☰ infantile epilepsy syndrome
 - ★ ● benign partial infantile seizures
 - idiopathic hemiconvulsion-hemiplegia syndrome
 - ★ ● infant epilepsy with migrant focal crisis
 - infantile spasms-broad thumbs syndrome
 - ★ ● infantile-onset mesial temporal lobe epilepsy with severe cognitive regression
 - ★ ● myoclonic epilepsy in non-progressive encephalopathies
 - ★ ● progressive myoclonic epilepsy with dystonia
 - ★ ● SYNGAP1-related developmental and epileptic encephalopathy
 - ★ ● undetermined early-onset epileptic encephalopathy

Note: This term is no longer in ILAE but it is used in Orphanet to group a number of terms (indicated with a ★)

Question:

Should we keep this based on Orphanet's usage or Obsolete because ILAE does not use it and reclassify children as subtypes of neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome?

'neonatal epilepsy syndrome' (MONDO:0020070)

neonatal epilepsy syndrome

- ★ benign idiopathic neonatal seizures
- ★ benign neonatal seizures
- ★ malignant migrating partial seizures of infancy
- neonatal-onset developmental and epileptic encephalopathy
- ★ severe neonatal-onset encephalopathy with microcephaly
- ★ undetermined early-onset epileptic encephalopathy

Comment (on term): This type of grouping class represents an older way of classifying diseases, and represented here <https://www.epilepsydiagnosis.org/index.html>.

Note: This term is no longer in ILAE but it is used in Orphanet to group a number of terms (indicated with a ★)

Proposal:

- Merge with neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome (or obsolete and consider 'neonatal/infantile epilepsy syndrome' as the recommended term)

Developmental and epileptic encephalopathy

- DEE should not be a child of 'epilepsy, idiopathic generalized'
- Assertion came from DOID:2481
- Addressed in:
<https://github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo/issues/8221>
 - Changes have not been released yet so they are not visible in OLS at the moment

